

1 **ANALYZING CYCLING BEHAVIOR AND TRAFFIC STATE INTERACTIONS AT**
2 **UNSIGNALIZED INTERSECTIONS USING BIRD’S-EYE VIEW VIDEO DATA**

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1 ABSTRACT

2 This study investigates cycling behavior in relation to the traffic state of the forward area using
3 multi-modal trajectories from bird's-eye view video data. Cycling is recognized as a sustainable
4 mode of transportation, with cities promoting urban designs to encourage it. However, the rise
5 in cyclist numbers has led to more accidents, especially in mixed traffic areas such as unsignal-
6 ized intersections. Despite its importance, cycling behavior remains under-researched compared
7 to car traffic due to the complexity of modeling non-lane-based movements and data collection
8 limitations. Existing models focus on specific interactions, but robust and comprehensive models
9 that consider various traffic situations are still lacking. This study addresses this gap by analyz-
10 ing cycling behavior based on the surrounding traffic state, particularly forward speed and lateral
11 fluctuations. Occupancy inside the intersection is considered a traffic state factor that may affect
12 behavior. Using bird's-eye view video data from Munich, multi-modal trajectories are extracted
13 and labeled by traffic mode based on the YOLO algorithm.

14 Correlation analysis reveals significant differences between lateral and forward speed fluc-
15 tuations, indicating two types of cyclists, with the majority detouring for collision avoidance rather
16 than waiting. Forward speed and occupancy also show different significant correlations for the
17 cyclists tending to detour in congested versus less congested situations. Insights from this study
18 can help develop robust models for estimating the impact of cycling behavior on other road users,
19 adaptable to different traffic scenarios and infrastructure designs, and from other users to bicyclists.
20 Applications for this research include microscopic models and vehicle collision avoidance models.

21

22 *Keywords:* cycling behavior analysis, unsignalized intersection, cycling collision avoidance, cy-
23 cling trajectory analysis, traffic safety

1 INTRODUCTION

2 Cycling is increasingly receiving attention as a sustainable and healthy mode of transportation from
3 policymakers and researchers. Many cities, including Munich, propose bicycle-friendly urban
4 planning designs that encourage cycling by enhancing road infrastructures and traffic regulations.
5 Despite these efforts, the rise in the number of cyclists (and hence exposure) has led to a corre-
6 sponding increase in cycling conflicts and accidents. For instance, the Netherlands is renowned
7 for being one of the pioneering countries of successful cycling promotion and has two of its major
8 cities ranked among the top three in the 2019 Copenhagenize Index (1) for bike-friendliness. How-
9 ever, Statistics Netherlands (2) reports an alarming rise in fatal bicycle accidents, contrasting with
10 the overall decline in road fatalities. Mixed traffic environments, particularly at unsignalized inter-
11 sections, pose significant risks as they involve complex interactions among cyclists, pedestrians,
12 and vehicles from various directions. Notably, in 2019, 17% of accidents occurred at intersections,
13 with cyclist fatalities being disproportionately higher than those on the road stretches because of
14 the higher number of conflict points (3). Cyclists' collision avoidance behaviors, such as sudden
15 braking and unexpected turns, further contribute to unsafe and stressful conditions for other road
16 users (4, 5).

17 Despite the increasing need for research in this area, studies focusing on cycling behavior
18 remain limited compared to those on car traffic. This gap exists for several reasons. Firstly, mod-
19 eling cycling movement is complex and differs significantly from lane-based car driving behavior.
20 Field observations by Huang and Wu (6) revealed that cyclists typically detour to avoid conflicts
21 rather than wait. Secondly, the data required to analyze cycling behavior is challenging to obtain
22 due to the small size and rapid movements of bicycles. Necessitating, for example, high-quality
23 GPS tracking and specifically tailored recording by videos and drones, limits the analysis data size
24 for targeting behavior and situations. Additionally, cycling behavior may be affected by several
25 varied factors such as traffic situations (7), infrastructure designs (8–10), environment (11, 12),
26 and cyclist and trip types (13, 14). Due to these limitations, existing cycling models often focus
27 on specific scenarios, such as following or overtaking another bicycle and crossing signalized or
28 unsignalized intersections. A comprehensive understanding of cycling behavior and its impact on
29 other road users requires a robust model that accounts for diverse situations, users, and infrastruc-
30 ture designs.

31 This study aims to investigate cycling behavior with a focus on forward-point traffic states.
32 Specifically, we examine fluctuations in forward speed and lateral movements, which are crucial
33 parameters affecting the behavior of other traffic participants (7, 15). We analyze mixed traffic at
34 a high-volume unsignalized intersection involving pedestrians, cyclists, and cars. Trajectories are
35 extracted and labeled by traffic mode using the YOLO algorithm (16) from bird's-eye view video
36 data recorded in Munich. While this study does not account for detailed environmental differences
37 and the modes of transportation of other road users, the insights gained will be applicable to various
38 scenarios, such as mixed shared roads and high cycling volumes in bidirectional bicycle lanes,
39 irrespective of infrastructure designs. The findings of this study will contribute to the development
40 of robust and macroscopic cycling models in consideration of multi-modal traffic impacts, such as
41 analyzing the impact of cyclists' collision avoidance behaviors on traffic states and safety.

1 LITERATURE REVIEW

2 **Microscopic Cycling Behavior Model**

3 In recent years, various models have been developed to understand and simulate microscopic cy-
4 cling behavior in response to different traffic modes. To explain lane-free traffic behavior and inter-
5 actions between traffic participants, Helbing and Molnár (17) introduced the Social Force Model,
6 which uses the concept of attractive virtual forces for pedestrians. This concept is often applied in
7 cycling behavior models. Treiber and Chaudhari (18) extended car-following models to lane-free
8 contexts by integrating them with the Social Force Model. Huang et al. (19) applied fuzzy logic
9 and social force theory to model cyclist behavior at unsignalized intersections with heterogeneous
10 traffic. Similarly, Li et al. (20) extended the Social Force Model to simulate bicycle operations at
11 high-density, mixed-traffic intersections.

12 Collision avoidance models have been developed to investigate conflicts involving cyclists,
13 primarily using traffic simulators (15). In these models, speed and turning angle are key parameters
14 for describing cycling behavior. Calibrating these parameters has gained significant attention. For
15 instance, Zhang et al. (7) calibrated these parameters based on surveys about decision-making in
16 various traffic situations. Researchers such as Li et al. (21) and Lee et al. (22) conducted experi-
17 ments with sensor-equipped bikes and scooters to calibrate these parameters for collision avoidance
18 with obstacles.

19 Additionally, models have been developed to analyze specific parameters related to cyclist
20 recognition. For example, Dias et al. (23) proposed a time-delayed acceleration model based on
21 interactions between cyclists. Recognition parameters such as reaction time and agility have been
22 measured in controlled experiments (24) and naturalistic field studies (25).

23 While existing cycling models focus on avoidance and reaction behavior towards other traf-
24 fic participants, these reactions may vary in different traffic states. Although collision-avoidance
25 models for cars consider the traffic state in the forward direction (26), similar models for cycling
26 behavior that account for traffic state are lacking.

27 **Cycling Trajectory Analysis**

28 Cycling behavior analysis has been conducted using trajectory data with several focuses. GPS-
29 detected trajectories are often used to analyze decision-making for cycling trips. Jeffrey Hood and
30 Charlton (27) and Huber used GPS data to study route choice. Amini et al. (28) and Kathis et al.
31 (29) analyzed path choice within signalized intersections based on trajectories captured by video
32 and cycling simulator experiments.

33 Few studies use trajectory data to analyze maneuvering behaviors such as speed, accel-
34 eration, and turning. Twaddle and Grigoropoulos (30) examined these behaviors at signalized
35 intersections, while Zhang et al. (7) focused on unsignalized intersections. Yan (31) investigated
36 speed variance and influencing factors using GPS data.

37 Cycling behavior differences based on cyclist classifications have also been analyzed using
38 GPS trajectory data. Poliziani et al. (13) explored these differences, while Bao et al. (14) analyzed
39 naturalistic cycling routes of children. Łukawska et al. (32) examined route choice differences
40 between infrequent and frequent cyclists. Grigoropoulos et al. (33) and Li et al. (20) focused on
41 group cycling categorization based on video recordings at intersections.

42 While correlations between driving behaviors such as acceleration and turning angle with
43 forward traffic state have been investigated for cars (34), similar studies for bicycles are still absent.

FIGURE 1: Study intersection on Open Street Map (35) and video data image. The blue polygon in (a) corresponds to the area recorded in (b).

1 DATA PROCESSING

2 Study Area and Data

3 The video data for this study was recorded from a bridge connecting buildings above the northeast
 4 approach of the intersection at Tal Street, Sparkassen Street, and Viktualienmarkt in the historic
 5 city center of Munich, Germany, as shown in blue polygon in Figure 1(a). This intersection experi-
 6 ences high volumes of pedestrians and cyclists due to its touristic central location and its inclusion
 7 in one of the main cycling routes through the city center. Sparkassen Street is designated as a bicy-
 8 cle boulevard (Fahrradstraße), which typically features low-speed limits and prioritizes free-flow
 9 travel for bicycles. Consequently, motorized traffic in this area is relatively low, consisting mainly
 10 of taxis and a limited number of business and private vehicles, and circulates at low-moderate
 11 speeds.

12 The video recordings were captured from a stationary camera positioned at a high angle to
 13 encompass the entire intersection, as depicted in Figure 1(b). The specific videos used in this study
 14 were recorded over 3 hours during the daytime on weekdays in the end of May, with a frame rate
 15 of 29.94 fps (36). This setup allowed for detailed observation and analysis of the interactions and
 16 movements of various traffic participants, providing a comprehensive dataset. Approximately 100
 17 minutes of video with good weather and high cyclist volume was chosen for this study.

18 Trajectory Extraction

19 Trajectory and Object Detection

20 To extract multimodal trajectories from video data with labels of object names, the You Only Look
 21 Once (YOLO) model, initially developed by (37), is applied in this study. This model is used
 22 in various fields for video data processing from image pixels to identify bounding boxes and class
 23 probabilities. This model has undergone numerous updates to enhance its speed and accuracy (38).
 24 In this study, we utilized the state-of-the-art YOLO-v8.2.38 (16), released in 2023 by Ultralytics.

1 *Filtering and Smoothing Trajectories*

2 The YOLO algorithm detects a bounding box with the four corner points of each object in every
3 video frame. For trajectory extraction, we use the midpoint of the bottom two x-pixel points of
4 the box as the x-coordinate, and the bottom point as the y-coordinate, representing the standing
5 location of the object.

6 YOLO sometimes detects bicycles and their riders as separate objects, leading to inter-
7 rupted trajectories that are later detected again under different IDs. To address this, overlapping
8 trajectories with different IDs are identified based on the ratio of synchronized paths and then
9 merged. When a cyclist is detected both as a bike and a person, the merged trajectory is labeled as
10 a bike.

11 Due to occasional detection failures by YOLO, filtering and compensating data sets are
12 necessary. Trajectories appearing for less than 30 frames (approximately 1 second) are removed.
13 Additionally, trajectories with a total movement of less than 1 pixel throughout the recording are
14 discarded as they likely represent parked cars or stationary obstacles, which are not relevant to
15 traffic dynamics inside the intersection. Anomalous points in trajectories with jumps greater than
16 0.01 pixels between frames are removed and replaced with the midpoint of the preceding and
17 succeeding points. Through the entire filtering and smoothing process, approximately 10% of
18 detected cycling trajectories are discarded or combined.

19 *Projection of Detected Road Users into Geographic Coordinates*

20 To calculate the position, speed, and acceleration of each detected road user in physical units, pixel-
21 space coordinates were converted to world-space coordinates in the Universal Transverse Mercator
22 (UTM) projection. Notable features, such as manhole covers and pavement joints visible in both
23 the captured images and satellite imagery, were used to determine pixel-space and UTM coordi-
24 nates. These coordinates and pre-calibrated intrinsic camera parameters were used to estimate a
25 homography matrix via the "findHomography()" function of the OpenCV library, representing the
26 transformation between the two coordinate systems.

27 *Target Trajectory Selection*

28 In this study, to focus on the effect of traffic state on cycling behavior fluctuations, turning trajec-
29 tories were removed from the target trajectories. Furthermore, due to the camera's mounted location,
30 only those labeled as bicycles moving straight from Sparkassen Street to Viktualienmarkt (bottom
31 to top of the video frames) were selected from the extracted trajectories.

32 Ultimately, we selected 127 cyclist trajectories out of a total of 414 as target trajectories to
33 analyze their cycling behaviors. Over the total recording period of 99 minutes, we observed 376
34 cars and 12,208 pedestrians. Detected trajectories of other traffic participants were used for traffic
35 state calculation.

36 **CALIBRATION OF KEY PARAMETERS**

37 To investigate the effect of traffic state on fluctuations in cycling behavior, we considered the
38 occupancy of the target area as a traffic state parameter and examined fluctuations in lateral and
39 forward movements to assess their impact on cycling behavior.

FIGURE 2: Occupancy calculation at an example frame. The yellow square shows the intersection area and the orange square shows the entrance area for both (a) and (b). Green, red, and blue circles in (b) represent effective spaces for cars, bikes, and pedestrians, respectively.

1 Traffic State of the Target Area

2 The target area is defined as the region where cyclists focus when determining their maneuvers,
 3 analogous to a fixation point. In this study, given that the bottom of the video frame is close
 4 (approximately 5 meters) to the intersection and cyclists typically fixate at distances greater than
 5 35 meters at signalized intersections (39), we assumed that the target area for most cyclists in
 6 our videos is within the intersection. The intersection area was manually delineated based on the
 7 infrastructure layout in the videos and coordinated map points, as shown by the yellow polygon
 8 in Figure 2(a). The intersection area often has a high volume of pedestrians, cyclists, and cars
 9 crossing from all possible directions. The entrance area, which cyclists traverse before entering
 10 the intersection, is shown by the orange polygon in Figure 2(a). Compared to the intersection area,
 11 the traffic flow within the entrance area mainly consists of a two-directional flow of pedestrians
 12 crossing the roads and slow right-turning cars from Tal Street. Notably, since the entrance area is
 13 on Sparkassen Street, which is a bicycle boulevard, many cyclists enter this area at free-flow speed
 14 when fewer pedestrians are crossing.

15 For vehicle collision avoidance models, the occupancy of other traffic participants is a
 16 crucial parameter representing traffic state (26, 40). To calculate the occupancy ρ_r for each time
 17 span within the target area, the "effective spaces" of cars, bikes, and pedestrians were estimated.
 18 In lane-based vehicle models, effective vehicle length, which represents the space occupied by a
 19 vehicle at jam density and is typically longer than the actual length, is used to calculate traffic
 20 density. We extended this concept to a two-dimensional area, considering all traffic modes.

21 Typically, the effective length of a vehicle ranges from 5 to 10 meters; we assumed it to
 22 be 6 meters in this study. For a 2D area, the effective space of a vehicle was calculated as
 23 by multiplying the effective length and the assumed lane width of 3.5 meters. For bike traffic, the
 24 maximum jam density at intersections is reported to be around 0.65 bikes/m² (41), yielding an
 25 effective space of approximately 1.53 m² per bike. According to Weidmann (42), the maximum

FIGURE 3: Calculation of forward and lateral fluctuations

1 pedestrian density is around 5.3 persons/m^2 , which is about 0.19 m^2 per person. Although actual
 2 densities in normal traffic situations are generally lower than jam density, using these values for
 3 occupancy calculations ensures that theoretical maximum occupancy is not exceeded.

4 Occupancy for each frame was calculated by summing the effective spaces of all traffic
 5 participants according to their traffic mode within the target area and then dividing by the area
 6 size. This calculation was performed every 10 frames (approximately every 0.34 seconds). Figure
 7 2(b) illustrates the detected effective spaces with circular shapes for different traffic modes (cars
 8 in green, bikes in red, and pedestrians in blue). Since occupancy is calculated based on effective
 9 space size, the shape of the space is not critical. It is important to note that this value differs from
 10 the area in the Social Force Model (17). The social force area refers to the interactive distance
 11 that influences the behavior of other traffic participants, whereas the effective space represents the
 12 recognized traffic density in the area by cyclists.

13 Cycling Behavior

14 To assess cycling fluctuations that may negatively impact other traffic participants, we considered
 15 forward speed, forward speed fluctuation, and lateral movement as key parameters. To calculate
 16 these parameters, the forward direction of a cyclist at time t is first defined as the direction of
 17 movement from $t-1$ to t , indicated by a dashed arrow in Figure 3. The longitudinal moving
 18 distance $d_y(t)$ is calculated as the difference in location between $t+1$ and t in the forward direction.
 19 Forward speed $v(t)$ is then calculated by dividing the longitudinal distance by the time span, as
 20 $v(t) = d_y(t)/\Delta t$. Forward speed fluctuation $f_v(t)$ is calculated as the absolute value of forward
 21 acceleration as:

$$22 \quad f_v(t) = |v(t) - v^*(t-1)|/\Delta t \quad (1)$$

23 where $v^*(t-1)$ is the speed in the actual direction at time $t-1$.

24 Lateral fluctuation is determined by the change in angle relative to the cyclist's location at
 25 $t+1$ and the forward direction. It is calculated using the arctangent of the longitudinal distance
 26 $d_y(t)$ at time $t+1$ and t and the lateral distance $d_x(t)$ between the actual location at $t+1$ and the
 27 forward direction. This can be expressed as:

$$28 \quad \theta(t) = \arctan\left(\frac{d_x(t+1)}{d_y(t)}\right) \quad (2)$$

29 where d_x is the lateral distance and d_y is the lateral distance. Time periods are converted from
 30 frames to seconds using the video frame rate.

(a) Forward acceleration

(b) Lateral fluctuation

FIGURE 4: Aggregated dynamics (mean: black bold line, std: filled in gray) of cycling fluctuation parameters according to longitudinal locations at the entrance area (orange background zone) and the intersection area (yellow background zone)

1 RESULTS

2 To validate the correlation analysis, we employed the Pearson correlation coefficient (43), a well-
 3 known linear regression test for two variables. The Pearson correlation coefficient ranges from -1
 4 to 1 , where 1 indicates the strongest positive correlation, -1 the strongest negative correlation, and
 5 0 no correlation. A p-value less than 0.05 indicates that the correlation is significant.

6 Cycling Behavior Analysis

7 Before analyzing the effect of traffic state, we first examined the cycling behavior observed in
 8 this study. Figure 4 shows the mean value and standard deviation (as black line and gray areas)
 9 of all target cyclists' forward acceleration and lateral fluctuation over the distance through the
 10 intersection area. The yellow zone represents the intersection area, and the orange zone represents
 11 the entrance area.

12 From Figure 4(a), we observe that the average forward acceleration decreases as cyclists
 13 approach the intersection area. The mean forward acceleration in the entrance area is 0.814 m/s^2
 14 with a standard deviation of 0.276 m/s^2 . In contrast, within the intersection area, cyclists exhibit
 15 minimal acceleration or even deceleration, with a mean forward acceleration of 0.167 m/s^2 and
 16 a standard deviation of 0.124 m/s^2 . The reduction in acceleration near the entrance area can be
 17 attributed to the high pedestrian flow in both directions, causing cyclists to frequently brake and
 18 change direction. The initial high acceleration at the entrance area is likely a result of cyclists
 19 accelerating after avoiding pedestrians, transitioning from very low speeds. Conversely, the inter-
 20 section area has multi-directional pedestrian movements, allowing cyclists to anticipate and avoid
 21 pedestrians more smoothly, resulting in stable acceleration close to 0 m/s^2 .

22 In Figure 4(b), the average lateral fluctuation in both the entrance and intersection areas
 23 does not show a notable difference. The mean lateral fluctuation is 0.019 rad in the entrance area
 24 and 0.012 rad in the intersection area. However, the standard deviation is larger in the entrance area
 25 (0.007 rad) compared to the intersection area (0.002 rad), indicating more frequent collision avoid-
 26 ance maneuvers at the entrance. Some instances of high standard deviation within the intersection
 27 area also suggest sudden collision avoidance behaviors.

FIGURE 5: Mean forward speed distribution of individual cyclists

1 Figure 5 presents the distribution of average speeds of individual cyclists, ranging from the
 2 slowest at almost 0 m/s to the fastest at around 9.5 m/s. The mean of average individual speed is
 3 5.23 m/s and standard deviation (std) 1.73 m/s.

4 **Correlation between Cycling Behavior Parameters**

5 The correlation between cycling behavior parameters is first considered to investigate the character-
 6 istics and interactions between these parameters. Figure 6 shows the correlation between average
 7 lateral fluctuation and average forward speed in (a) and average forward acceleration in (b). In
 8 Figure 6 (a), when the average lateral fluctuation is less than 0.007 rad, the scatter has strong pos-
 9 itive correlation (Coefficient: 0.708, P-value:5.1e-05). When the fluctuation is larger than 0.007
 10 rad, the scatter is in the moderate negative correlation (Coefficient: -0.49, P-value:1.1e-07). Some
 11 plots have low average forwarding speeds, such as 0 to 5 m/s. When lateral fluctuation is smaller
 12 than 0.007 [rad], it shows the movement of cyclists who tend to wait or slow down to avoid colli-
 13 sions. High average forwarding speed, such as around 6 to 9 m/s, with smaller lateral fluctuation
 14 shows the cyclists who did not face to high occupancy situation or at least found no obstacles on
 15 their path. Negative correlation when the lateral fluctuation is large can be derived from cyclists
 16 who tend to detour for collision avoidance. Large variance in forwarding speed derived from the
 17 speed variation of each cyclists. As mentioned in Huang and Wu (6), the majority of the detected
 18 cyclists in this study (79.8% excluding the cyclists who did not face high occupancy or collision
 19 avoidance situations) tend to detour rather than wait.

20 In Figure 6 (b), shows the significant positive correlation between lateral fluctuation and
 21 forwarding speed fluctuation (Coefficient: 0.253, P-value: 0.01) for the cyclists who tends to
 22 detour for collision avoidance with the lateral fluctuation higher than 0.007 rad. Both parameters
 23 are higher when they face higher occupancy for those types of cyclists. This higher speed and
 24 lateral fluctuations are likely engaging in more aggressive maneuvers to avoid collisions, which
 25 disrupts the flow and stability of traffic safety and state. The variance in speed comes from the
 26 different regular cycling between individuals as shown in Figure 5. On the other hand, when the
 27 lateral fluctuation is lower than 0.007 rad for cyclists who tends to wait rather than detour, average
 28 speed fluctuation is always high as around 0.5 m/s² to 1.2 m/s² except for cyclists who did not face
 29 the high occupancy with very low speed fluctuation (lower than 0.4 m/s²) and almost 0 rad lateral

(a) Lateral fluctuation vs average forward speed

(b) Lateral fluctuation vs average forward-speed fluctuation

FIGURE 6: Correlations between cycling behavior parameters (vertical dash line shows the lateral fluctuation threshold 0.007 rad, black lines show the linear fit lines)

FIGURE 7: Average traffic occupancy faced by individual cyclists at the intersection area (yellow) and the entrance area (orange) (black dash line shows the median value at the intersection area)

1 fluctuation. This behavior indicates that these cyclists react with sudden braking and accelerating
2 when encountering potential collisions, rather than gradually avoiding obstacles.

3 Correlation between Traffic State and Cycling Behavior

4 To analyze the effect of traffic state on cycling behavior, traffic occupancy was calculated for both
5 the intersection area and the entrance area. The distribution of average traffic occupancy faced
6 by individual cyclists is shown in Figure 7, with yellow representing the intersection area and
7 orange representing the entrance area. In the intersection area, most cyclists encountered very
8 low occupancy, typically below 1%. However, some cyclists faced higher occupancy, averaging
9 around 6% to 8%, due to the presence of groups of pedestrians, other cyclists, and cars. The median
10 occupancy value for all cyclists in the intersection area is 0.83%, as indicated by the black dashed
11 line. Figure 8 shows the example of very high (a) and very low (b) occupancy situations at the
12 intersection. In contrast, in the entrance area, most cyclists faced higher occupancy compared to the

(a) Very high occupancy

(b) Very low occupancy

FIGURE 8: Example video frames of very high and low occupancy situations

1 intersection area, with a mean value of 2.85%. This difference in distribution is due to the narrower
2 space and occasionally high density of crossing pedestrians in the entrance area. The median
3 occupancy value faced by all cyclists in the entrance area was used to categorize two traffic states:
4 "high occupancy," when the value is larger than the median, indicating a congested situation, and
5 "low occupancy," when the value is smaller than the median, indicating a less congested situation.

6 Occupancy and cycling behavior parameters at the intersection area were compared to as-
7 sess correlations, as shown in Figure 9. Red plots indicate the correlation for cyclists with larger
8 average lateral fluctuation (those who tend to detour for collision avoidance). The correlation is
9 significantly negative (Pearson Correlation Coefficient: -0.29, P-value: 0.0048), indicating that
10 cyclists move slower in the forward direction by detouring when they encounter higher occupancy.
11 In contrast, the plots for cyclists with smaller average lateral fluctuation (those who tend to wait for
12 collision avoidance) are scattered, showing no clear correlation. This lack of correlation may stem
13 from the cognitive behavior characteristics of these cyclists, who tend to focus on the single closest
14 obstacle on their path regardless of the overall traffic state. In contrast, cyclists who tend to detour
15 are more attentive to the overall traffic state of the area. Understanding the factors behind these dif-
16 ferent behaviors requires deeper cognitive analysis, such as field experiments with eye-tracking to
17 study cyclists' focus and decision-making processes in various traffic states, or intercept surveys.

18 On the other hand, no significant correlation was found between occupancy and other cy-
19 cling behavior parameters such as forward acceleration and lateral fluctuation, as shown in Figure
20 10. Categorizing cyclists into fast and slow groups based on the median speed, where the mean
21 (std) average speed of the slower group is 4.33 m/s (1.15 m/s) and the mean (std) average speed of
22 the faster group is 6.81 m/s (0.92 m/s), also did not improve the correlation in these parameters.
23 The likely reason for this is that acceleration and lateral fluctuation parameters are highly sensitive
24 to individual collision avoidance reactions. For example, a single sudden brake or detour to avoid
25 an obstacle can result in a significantly low forward acceleration, regardless of the overall traffic
26 state. Due to the complex interactions between these parameters, a deeper empirical and theoret-
27 ical analysis is needed, including categorizing the types of collision avoidance behavior, to identify
28 additional key factors influencing these behaviors.

FIGURE 9: Correlation between average traffic occupancy faced by cyclists and individual average forwarding speed at the intersection area (red line show linear fit for cyclists tend to detour.)

(a) Average forward speed fluctuation

(b) Average lateral fluctuation

FIGURE 10: Correlation between average traffic occupancy and cycling behavior parameters at the intersection area

1 CONCLUSION

2 This paper investigates cycling behavior, focusing on forward speed and lateral fluctuation, in
 3 relation to the forward traffic state. The analysis is based on bird's-eye view video footage recorded
 4 at an unsignalized mixed-traffic intersection. Trajectories of all traffic participants were extracted
 5 and labeled by their mode of transportation using the YOLO algorithm. These trajectories were
 6 then projected from pixel-space to world-space coordinates using the UTM projection. Only one-
 7 way straight cycling trajectories were selected and filtered to eliminate misclassifications by the
 8 algorithm. From these trajectories, forward direction, speed, acceleration, and lateral fluctuation
 9 were calculated.

10 The results reveal several significant correlations between key parameters. Specifically,
 11 we identified two distinct trends in the relationship between lateral fluctuation and forward speed
 12 fluctuation, divided by a lateral fluctuation threshold of 0.007 radians. For smaller lateral fluctua-
 13 tions, a positive correlation indicates that cyclists tend to wait rather than detour when faced with

1 a collision avoidance situation. For larger lateral fluctuations, a negative correlation indicates that
2 cyclists are more likely to detour to avoid collisions. Consistent with existing literature, our study
3 found that approximately 80% of cyclists tend to detour when encountering potential collisions,
4 excluding those who did not face any such situation.

5 Cyclists who detour in high-occupancy situations exhibit increased average speed and lat-
6 eral fluctuations, which may lead to further conflicts with other traffic participants. The average
7 forward speed of these cyclists is significantly negatively affected by the area's traffic occupancy.
8 In contrast, cyclists who tend to wait show no significant correlation between occupancy and for-
9 ward speed, likely because they focus on obstacles directly in their path rather than the broader
10 traffic state. No significant correlation was found between occupancy and other behavior param-
11 eters such as speed and lateral fluctuations for the waiting cyclists. Further experimental data,
12 particularly from a cognitive science perspective, could provide deeper insights into cycling be-
13 havior parameters and cyclist categorization.

14 The findings of this study can be instrumental in developing robust cycling behavior mod-
15 els applicable to various traffic situations. Additionally, understanding the influence of cyclist
16 behavior on traffic safety and state can inform better traffic management and safety interventions.

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23 The authors confirm their contribution to the paper as follows: study conception and design: A.
24 Takayasu, P.Malcolm, A. Moreno, K. Bogenberger; data collection and filtering: A. Takayasu,
25 P.Malcolm; analysis and interpretation of results: A. Takayasu; draft manuscript preparation: A.
26 Takayasu, P.Malcolm, A. Moreno and K. Bogenberger. All authors reviewed the results and ap-
27 proved the final version of the manuscript.

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